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Earth Observation for Justice in Gaza: Ethical and Legal Implications

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Abstract

Earth Observation (EO) has the potential to play a transformative role in documenting genocide in Gaza, supporting accountability efforts, and advancing justice. However, access to satellite imagery and the ability to analyze it remains highly unequal. The communities most affected often lack the resources, funding, and political leverage needed to obtain and utilize EO data effectively. As a result, systematic destruction and human rights violations risk remaining underreported or invisible, limiting the ability of local actors to advocate for justice and recognition. Despite the availability of EO technologies, significant barriers exist in applying this data for humanitarian and legal purposes. High-resolution satellite imagery is often restricted, leaving affected populations reliant on lower-resolution or outdated datasets. By highlighting these barriers, this research underscores the urgent need for ethical frameworks that ensure EO is used for justice rather than reinforcing existing power asymmetries. Furthermore, this study explores the legal applications of satellite imagery as evidence in international accountability mechanisms, including its potential role in supporting cases at the International Court of Justice (ICJ). Satellite data has increasingly been used as evidence in genocide investigations, and its integration into justice frameworks could strengthen efforts to hold responsible parties accountable. However, geopolitical control over EO data raises ethical concerns about whose experiences are validated and whose remain obscured. Beyond legal applications, EO can empower local communities by providing scientific evidence of atrocities and destruction, supporting advocacy and accountability initiatives. This work examines the ethical and legal dimensions through a case study focusing on Gaza. It calls for a decolonial approach to space technologies, where EO is leveraged not as a tool of surveillance and geopolitical control, but as an instrument of justice and accountability for those most impacted by genocide. By addressing both the ethical and legal challenges of EO for justice in Gaza, this research advocates for a more inclusive and ethical use of space technology, ensuring satellite data is mobilized to document genocide and actively support accountability efforts.

Keywords: Earth Observation, Gaza, Legal Framework, Ethics, Accountability, Genocide

Acronyms

EO	Earth Observation
ICJ	International Court of Justice
ICC	International Criminal Court
PSI	Palestine Space Institute

The Palestine Space Institute (PSI) is a pioneering and visionary think tank that stands at the forefront of space ethics and the responsible use of outer space [4]. This project falls under PSI's theme "Space for Palestine," feeding into a new EO research direction. PSI argues that space must be decoupled from militarism and dual-use logics, positioning EO as a tool of justice rather than surveillance. By reframing space technologies through a decolonial lens, PSI seeks to ensure that EO supports accountability for genocide rather than reinforcing inequities.

1. Introduction

The genocide in Gaza has been characterized by systematic destruction of civilian infrastructure, mass killings, and conditions deliberately created to bring about the destruction of the Palestinian people [1]. EO technologies provide independent, verifiable evidence where humanitarian observers and journalists have been restricted or targeted. Satellite imagery has recorded neighborhoods erased in days, hospitals and schools bombed, and farmland destroyed [2,3]. These records are vital to accountability as they reveal intent and scale in ways that cannot be obscured by political denial.

2. Challenges and Censorship

The potential of EO for accountability in Gaza is limited by unequal access. High-resolution commercial imagery is expensive and often licensed in ways that prevent humanitarian actors or local communities from using it. This reflects a wider problem of epistemic injustice,

where those most affected by atrocities lack access to the tools that could substantiate their experiences in international fora.

Geopolitical controls have also undermined visibility. The U.S. Kyl-Bingaman Amendment of 1997 prohibited distribution of high-resolution imagery of occupied Palestine [5]. For decades, this obstructed accountability for settlement expansion, forced displacement, and destruction of Palestinian land. Even after restrictions were reduced in 2020, the damage to timely recognition of atrocities was significant.

Restrictions on journalistic coverage have compounded these barriers. The Committee to Protect Journalists reported that 2024 was the deadliest year for journalists in its history, with almost 70% killed by Israel in Gaza [6]. With witnesses silenced or killed, EO becomes indispensable for preserving evidence of genocide.

3. Mapping Genocide in Gaza

EO has made it possible to measure the scale and systematic nature of destruction. UNOSAT reported that by December 2023, 18% of all structures in Gaza were damaged, including more than 10,000 completely destroyed [7]. A 2024 analysis confirmed that essential civilian infrastructure was disproportionately targeted: over 60% of health facilities, 68% of schools, and 42% of water and sanitation sites were hit, with clustering so pronounced that the likelihood of randomness was less than 1% [8].

Forensic Architecture documented the deliberate destruction of agricultural zones, orchards, and neighborhoods [2,3,9]. In some cases, as in Khuza'a in May 2025, the destruction extended beyond "combat zones," encompassing homes, farms, and greenhouses. These findings highlight how genocide operates not only through direct killings but through the imposition of life-destroying conditions. This environmental devastation demonstrates the use of ecocide as a weapon [2, 10].

PSI's Sentinel-2 study contributed to this evidentiary base by showing how open-source, medium-resolution EO can also track devastation. Using established environmental indices, it quantified damage to wastewater treatment facilities and surface water anomalies due to the genocide [10]. This demonstrated that even without commercial imagery, freely accessible EO can support accountability. Situating this work alongside higher-resolution and forensic analyses expands the methodological range available for documenting genocide.

4. Forced Displacement

Forced displacement has been one of the most visible and devastating aspects of the genocide in Gaza. On 13 October 2023, Israel ordered 1.1 million Palestinians to leave northern Gaza within 24 hours. EO imagery confirmed the rapid creation of bulldozed corridors, militarized checkpoints, and sealed zones that funneled civilians south [3]. By the end of the year, 1.9 million people, representing around 85% of Gaza's total population, had been displaced [3].

Satellite analysis has revealed that these evacuations were not temporary protective measures but deliberate strategies of control. Many of the so-called "safe zones" were subsequently bombed, while humanitarian convoys were obstructed. EO time-series datasets show how displacement routes correspond with later strikes, demonstrating that displacement functioned less as a protective policy and more as a tool of forced transfer [9].

In our study to assess environmental destruction in Gaza, we detected changes in land cover linked to the emergence of displacement camps that were incorrectly identified by EO as still water [10]. The results showed the importance of complementing EO analysis with detailed investigation and cross-referencing it with ground data.

Together, these records establish that forced displacement in Gaza was not incidental but systematic, implemented at unprecedented scale and speed. The evidence demonstrates how displacement itself has been weaponized as part of genocidal policy.

5. Digital Reconstruction and AI

Beyond static images, EO is increasingly combined with advanced methodologies to provide stronger accountability records. Forensic Architecture has produced three-dimensional reconstructions of strikes on sites such as Al-Shati refugee camp and Al-Ahli hospital, integrating EO with ground video, drone footage, and witness testimonies [2,9]. These models show strike origins, timelines, and munition types, providing spatially verifiable evidence admissible in international accountability mechanisms.

Artificial intelligence has also been applied to EO datasets in this direction. A 2024 study used deep learning to detect 3,747 bomb craters in Gaza, demonstrating a consistent pattern of disproportionate attacks on residential and educational structures [11]. The same study identified a 34% collapse in cultivated farmland, further exposing deliberate destruction of food systems.

While these methods scale and strengthen evidentiary value, they also raise ethical concerns. Automated damage mapping risks reducing atrocities to numerical outputs if divorced from the lived realities of survivors. A justice-centered approach must therefore combine AI-assisted EO with qualitative testimonies to ensure that technology amplifies rather than silences survivor voices.

6. Geopolitics and Legal Evidence

The integration of EO evidence into legal processes is increasingly relevant given the ongoing international proceedings on Gaza. On 29 December 2023, South Africa filed a case at the International Court of Justice (ICJ) accusing Israel of committing genocide in Gaza [12]. The ICJ's provisional measures order of 26 January 2024 recognized the plausibility of genocide and directed Israel to prevent genocidal acts and ensure humanitarian access [12]. EO evidence has played a key role in substantiating claims of systematic destruction of civilian infrastructure and mass displacement, strengthening the evidentiary record in support of South Africa's submission.

Parallel proceedings were happening at the International Criminal Court (ICC). In May 2024, the ICC Prosecutor announced applications for arrest warrants against Israeli officials, including Prime Minister Benjamin Netanyahu and Defense Minister Yoav Gallant, for war crimes and crimes against humanity [13]. Satellite analysis has been cited by human rights organizations as corroborating evidence of deliberate targeting of civilian areas, starvation of populations as a method of warfare, and destruction of protected infrastructure [2,3,8].

Historical precedent also supports the admissibility of EO as legal evidence. Satellite imagery was used by the ICC in Darfur [14], by the International Criminal Tribunal for the former Yugoslavia [15], and in European prosecutions of Syrian officials [16]. These cases illustrate that EO can meet evidentiary standards when supported by expert analysis, chain of custody protocols, and integration with testimonial and documentary evidence.

Despite this, challenges remain. Limited financial and technical resources inhibit the effective use of EO by humanitarian and legal actors. Crucially, however, the main obstacle is not technical but political. Without the will of international institutions and states to act, even overwhelming EO evidence risks being archived rather than mobilized for accountability.

7. Ethical and Decolonial Approach

The use of EO in Gaza demands a careful ethical framework. Palestinians already live under an extensive surveillance regime involving drones, biometric systems, and satellite monitoring. Repurposing EO for justice must therefore avoid reproducing these same systems of control. Instead, it must be mobilized within a decolonial framework that resists domination and reclaims visibility as a tool of accountability [4].

Central to this approach is the imperative not to dehumanize. The sheer scale of destruction captured by satellites can risk abstracting suffering into pixels, percentages, or damage indices. When neighborhoods are reduced to before-and-after images, or when casualties are counted without names or stories, technology risks stripping survivors of their humanity. An ethical approach insists that EO be used in ways that preserve dignity, contextualize data with lived testimony, and ensure that communities are represented not as objects of surveillance but as agents of justice.

This requires democratizing access to EO, particularly for affected communities, and ensuring that imagery is not monopolized by governments or corporations. Survivor voices must be centered alongside satellite analysis, so that the images of destroyed homes, schools, and farms are tied to the people whose lives have been uprooted. EO should amplify those voices, not erase them.

PSI's vision for EO as an epistemic technology of justice emphasizes transparency, accessibility, and equity. By reframing EO within a justice-centered epistemology, PSI challenges the historical alignment of space technologies with the military-industrial complex. Neutrality in the face of genocide constitutes complicity, and EO cannot be treated as detached observation. Instead, it must be actively mobilized to document violations, affirm dignity, and strengthen accountability.

8. From Visibility to Accountability

EO has provided undeniable visibility of genocide in Gaza [1,2,3]. The destruction of neighborhoods, the targeting of schools and hospitals, the erasure of farmland, and the displacement of nearly two million people have all been captured in satellite datasets [7,8,9]. Yet visibility is not the same as accountability. To stop at visibility risks treating Palestinians as mere objects of observation, their suffering reduced to abstract datasets.

International law makes clear that once genocide is visible, states have an obligation to act [1]. The ICJ proceedings initiated by South Africa [12] and the

ICC's arrest warrants against Israeli officials [13] confirm that this obligation is recognized. EO has accelerated awareness, making it increasingly difficult for states or institutions to continue engaging in genocide denial or claim ignorance. The challenge is to ensure that awareness translates into enforcement.

Moving from visibility to accountability requires integrating EO into legal, political, and moral frameworks. First, EO evidence must be preserved and presented with integrity, meeting standards of admissibility in courts. Second, it must be situated alongside survivor voices, so that images of destruction are not detached from the human lives they represent. Third, political will must be mobilized to act on the evidence.

Visibility without action risks dehumanization. Every image of rubble represents a home, a school, or a life. Accountability means refusing to treat EO as a detached record and instead using it as a catalyst for justice.

9. Conclusion

EO has become indispensable in documenting genocide in Gaza. It has measured destruction, tracked forced displacement, and corroborated survivor testimonies. It has strengthened the evidentiary base for legal proceedings at the ICJ and ICC, ensuring that genocidal acts cannot be concealed from international scrutiny [12,13].

Yet the significance of EO lies not only in making genocide visible, but in how that visibility is mobilized. Satellites cannot prevent atrocities, but they can remove the cover of denial. Justice requires that EO be used responsibly, ethically, and in ways that affirm dignity rather than reduce lives to abstractions.

PSI advances a vision of EO as an epistemic technology for justice. This means resisting its historical alignment with surveillance and militarism, ensuring access for affected communities, and embedding analysis within survivor-centered narratives.

Satellites cannot prevent genocide, but they ensure it cannot be concealed. The responsibility then lies with the international community to act on this evidence. Ultimately, neutrality in the face of genocide is complicity.

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